

APPLICATIONS OF OPTICS IN ARRAYS

Richard R. Kunath
NASA Lewis Research Center
Space Electronics Division
Cleveland, Ohio

INTRODUCTION

The development of array antennas for mm-wave communications systems has led to the investigation of optics to enable these applications. Fiber optics has been found to be particularly attractive for the distribution of both control and RF signals to phased array antenna modules. Additionally, fiber optic beam forming networks (BFNs) may be the only way to implement high gain, simultaneous, independent, multi-beam satellite communications antenna systems. Optics can also be used to implement optically processed BFNs (OPBFNs) that support phased array antennas, in which the necessary phase and amplitude excitations are created in the optical domain prior to being downconverted to an RF carrier. These optical technologies have been selected for investigation because they target potential technology breakthroughs which will enable future communications systems.

OPTICAL CONTROL SIGNAL DISTRIBUTION

During the integration of Monolithic Microwave Integrated Circuits (MMICs) into phased array antenna modules, it was determined that conventional control signal distribution systems were inappropriate for routing the MMIC control information to the MMICs in the phased array modules. Due to the number of interconnections and the limited surface area it was decided that the control signals should be multiplexed. To eliminate any potential EMI, optical interconnections were chosen, and an optoelectronic integrated circuit (OEIC) was developed. The initial array architectures considered one centralized antenna controller responsible for calculating and setting the individual element phase and amplitude excitations, which pushed the OEIC data rates into the hundreds of Mbps. Subsequent design iterations resulted in an OEIC with many advanced features.

The current OEIC design features the following characteristics. The OEIC is GaAs device in which a Metal-Semiconductor-Metal (MSM) photodetector, a low-noise amplifier (LNA), and a serial to parallel demultiplexer are integrated. The OEIC operates at variable data rates from 10 to 450 Mbps, and the data is encoded

U.S. Government work not protected by U.S. Copyright.

so that the clock signal necessary for demultiplexing can be sent with the data. The each OEIC is uniquely addressable, and data can be sent in either a CW or bursted mode. While the OEIC maximum power consumption is approximately 750 Mw, the OEIC can be placed in a "sleep" mode which reduces power consumption by 80%. Even though the OEIC was developed for phased array antenna use, it is also applicable to fiber optic local area networks and robotics applications.

OPTICAL RF SIGNAL DISTRIBUTION

The need for fiber optics to distribute mm-wave RF signals has become increasingly apparent for communications systems featuring array antennas. At mm-wave frequencies, the conventional signal distribution systems such as waveguide, coaxial cable, and microstrip are either too heavy, too lossy or too mechanically inflexible. Communications systems using multiple phased array modules require lightweight, low loss, mechanically flexible BFNs. Additionally, communications systems which require high gain, simultaneous, independent, multi-beam antenna systems need array feeds fed by multiple BFNs. Fiber optics enables these systems.

Fiber optics distribution systems are relatively lossless once the signal is in the fiber. However, the devices and technology to modulate and detect the optical carriers at mm-wave frequencies have been very limited. Two optical technologies that have been investigated at NASA Lewis to implement optical RF signal distribution are optically injection-locked oscillators, and polymer-based electrooptic modulators (EOMs).

In the optically injection-locked oscillator architecture, each MMIC module has a free-running mm-wave oscillator which is optically injection locked to a stable reference source via a fiber optic link. The same fiber optic link carries baseband communications data which is mixed with the optically injection-locked oscillator signal at the MMIC module. In general, the optical injection-locking reference signal is a subharmonic of the free-running MMIC module oscillator, which enables lower frequency semiconductor lasers and detectors to be utilized.

A recent addition to the Lewis program is the development of polymer-based EOMs. Due to the limited frequency modulation range of semiconductor laser diodes, EOMs have been investigated. An EOM is used with an unmodulated semiconductor laser to impress an

RF signal onto the optical carrier. Polymer-based EOMs have the potential to modulate optical carriers to 100 Ghz due to their inherently low dielectric constants. Additionally, the polymer materials are particularly inexpensive. The EOMs being investigated are traveling wave devices which use interferometric techniques to generate amplitude modulated optical signals.

OPTICALLY PROCESSED BEAM FORMING NETWORKS

OPBFNs have been investigated as an alternative method for creating mm-wave phased array antennas instead of using MMICs. In particular, OPBFNs have a potential application for a NASA mission in the exploration of Mars. In this application, a satellite in orbit around Mars would be used to retrieve data from multiple rovers on the Martian surface. The advantage of the OPBFN architecture is its ability to reconfigure simultaneous multiple beams easily.

The OPBFN system is based on a holographic technique. A single laser source is split into two independent beams. One beam is used to form spatial path, while the other forms a temporal path. In the spatial path is a spatial light modulator (SLM) which creates an optical analog of the multi-beam mm-wave antenna pattern. The SLM is placed at the forward focal point of a Fourier transforming lens (FTL). At the rear FTL focal point is a beam combiner, at which point the phases and amplitudes required by the mm-wave phased array have been created by the FTL. In the temporal path is an EOM which is modulated by the mm-wave communications signal. After an appropriate delay, the temporal optical signal is combined with the spatial optical signal at the beam combiner. The resultant optical field is composed of both the spatial and temporal information needed by the mm-wave phased array. This optical field is incident on a fiber optic bundle which spatially samples the optical field. The signal picked up by each fiber is routed to a corresponding element in the mm-wave phased array antenna. At the element it is detected, amplified, and radiated. A breadboard to demonstrate this process is currently under development.

CONCLUSION

NASA Lewis has been involved in the development of optical technologies to enable the implementation of mm-wave array antennas. The focus of the Lewis research has been in the areas of fiber optic control and RF signal distribution to support MMIC array designs,

and the development of optically processed BFNs. The development of these optical technologies is being pursued in an effort to enable mm-wave communication antenna systems which are limited by the signal distribution systems and antenna system architectures currently available.